

[View this email in your browser](#)

Welcome to our May 2022 newsletter

where we bring you news of past, present and future events and activities.

Registration is open for *International Data Week*, 20-23 June and a *3-day interactive online workshop*, June and July, on an *introduction to Spark with R and lazy evaluation* and the call for applications for the *Trieste Summer School*, 11-22 July opens soon. Further details for all below. For those of you under 30 and interested in submitting a policy paper, read about the opportunity in an open call with the *Journal of Science Policy & Governance*.

The **Data Schools Forum** is live so if you haven't yet registered read on for further details including a profile on Annajiat, one of our alumni who has volunteered to monitor the Forum.

We have our regular alumni profiles and our instructor profile is Louise Bezuidenhout who has been involved with the Summer Schools since the first school in Trieste 2016.

Find out about the newly established Data Schools Advisory Board, a recently launched Moodle course for online Data Steward training and access to the Spanish translation of Open and Responsible Science and Research Data Management materials from the Data Schools.

South Africa | São Paulo School of Research Data Science 9 May - 15 July 2022 - Online and Self-Paced

9th May saw the inauguration of the latest CODATA-RDA Data Science School. 52 participants - from South Africa, Nigeria, Ghana, Zimbabwe, Sudan, Kenya, Botswana and Indonesia - are taking part in the South Africa school and there are 49 attending the São Paulo school with attendees from Brazil, Argentina, Ecuador, Mexico, Cameroon, Kenya and Nigeria.

São Paulo website [here](#) for further information.

Journal of Science Policy & Governance (JSPG) Call for "Open Science"

JSPG has launched a call for "Open Science" as an upcoming special issue. JSPG is a unique journal, empowering Early Career Researchers (they could be research students, postdocs, policy fellows etc) aged 30 years and below to write a policy paper and publish in the journal. More interestingly, JSPG will organize several workshops to help ECRs build ideas and craft policy papers for submission to the "Open Science" special issue, which will be held in April 2022.

For further details please read [here](#).

Deadline for submission is 10 July 2022

Instructor Profile

Louise Bezuidenhout

Hi everyone, I'm Louise Bezuidenhout. Originally from South Africa, I currently work in the Netherlands at DANS (Data Archiving and Networked Services) as a data expert. My work at DANS focuses mainly on training and policy development, particularly in relation to the new European Open Science Cloud. This European focus is relatively new for me, as for the past 10 years I've been advocating for Open Science in low/middle-income countries. I still keep in

Open Science Platform.

As you might have guessed from the paragraph above, I'm not a data scientist. I've got a joint background in cell biology and sociology. My work focuses mainly on issues to do with responsibility and openness in research. My background makes me well-placed to talk to researchers about their data sharing challenges, and also to identify what aspects of their research environments help – or hinder – their efforts to make their data open and FAIR and their research responsible and transparent.

I've been involved with the CODATA-RDA Data Science Summer Schools since the first one was held in Trieste in 2016. I've been thrilled to develop the curriculum on open and responsible research that is taught in the schools. I feel that having an ethics component to our schools really makes us stand out against similar training, and provides our students with tools to confidently understand the responsibilities that they face as researchers.

My teaching – as many of the readers will know – is very hands on. I understand that having instruction in ethics and policy is very new to many of our students, and can feel overwhelming. Because of this I like to include a lot of discussion in my teaching, as well as the opportunity to raise personal concerns or perspectives. Unlike other modules on the school, there are no absolute answers in ethics, and no “one way” to be open and responsible. Responsibility, I always say, is a journey and our training is just one step in a lifelong journey.

Since 2018 I've been very honoured to be a co-chair of the schools, as well as the interim chair of the alumni working group. We are always looking for keen alumni to join the working group and to suggest new projects for our amazing (and growing) group of alumni to take on board. I look forward to meeting you all in future schools, in instructor training, in the alumni working group or at alumni events. Because, after all, we are not just a once-off training, but a vibrant community that links researchers across the world.

CODATA-RDA Research Data Science Summer School Trieste 2022 11 - 22 July 2022

An ICTP Hybrid Meeting, Trieste, Italy

We are pleased to announce this year's Summer School, Trieste, which will take place 11 to 22 July 2022 both online and in person. Call for applications is

for participants from all disciplines and/or backgrounds from sciences to humanities.

There is no registration fee and there are a limited number of grants available to support the attendance of selected participants from developing countries.

Please visit the [ICTP website](#) for further details and registration.

Deadline for in person attendance 1 June 2022 and for online attendance 24 June.

Spanish Translation of Materials - Open and Responsible Science and Research Data Management

Marcela Alfaro

We are pleased to announce that the material for the Open and Responsible Science and Research Data Management sections of the CODATA-RDA School of Research Data Science has been translated into Spanish.

This translation was done as a collaborative effort between La Referencia and CONARE (Consejo Nacional de Rectores, Costa Rica). The initiative was led by Andrea Mora Campos with the help of Viviana Salgado Silva. They both work in Open Science and Research Management, and were students and local hosts for the Costa Rican Data Stewardship school, in November 2020. After being part of the school, the need for a Spanish version of the materials was established, and Andrea decided to look for a way to fund the translation and recruit more people to complete it.

One year later, the funds were secured and the translation effort started. Federico Cetrángolo from LA Referencia joined the initiative, and Naomy Viquez Mora was hired as an assistant to complete the task. Andrea Méndez, a Spanish Philology faculty member at the Universidad Técnica Nacional and Universidad Nacional, Costa Rica, was in charge of preparing a first translation and reviewing the final version. In between, Mora Campos, Salgado Silva, Cetrángolo, and Viquez Mora were in charge of checking that the translation had the appropriate context, according to their expertise in Open Science and RDM.

The translations can be found here:

<https://www.datascienceschools.org/materials/>

- RDM: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6341868>

- Open and Responsible Research II:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6341968>

We are extremely thankful for this effort, and hope that it serves as a motivation for other groups to translate our material into other languages.

International Data Week (IDW) 20-23 June 2022

In-person and Virtual
Seoul, Republic of Korea

IDW brings together data scientists, researchers, industry leaders, entrepreneurs, policymakers and data stewards from disciplines across the globe to explore how best to exploit the data revolution to improve science and society through data-driven discovery and innovation.

This event - taking place every 2 years - combines the [RDA Plenary meeting](#), working to develop and support global infrastructure facilitating data sharing and reuse, and [SciDataCon](#), the scientific conference addressing the frontiers of data in research organised by CODATA and WDS.

[The Committee on Data \(CODATA\)](#).

[The Research Data Alliance \(RDA\)](#).

[The World Data System \(WDS\)](#).

For further details and registration visit the [International Data Week](#) or the [IDW2022](#) websites.

Early bird registration - special rates for students and LMICs - ends 31st May 2022

Introduction to Spark with R and Lazy evaluation

3-day workshop

An interactive online workshop for learning the basics of Spark in R and how to easily include lazy evaluation in a data analysis workflow.

As part of the CODATA Connect series, a 3-day workshop taking place 18 June, 25 June and 2 July, is being organised with the objective of sharing practical examples of how to implement Spark with R to a data science project

For further details and application please see [here](#).

Applications will close on 5 June 2022.

Data Schools Forum

The Data Schools Forum, hosted on our [website](#) is now live.

If you would like to be registered on the forum and you haven't yet sent us your confirmation please complete [this Google form](#).

The Forum is the place to:

- raise questions
- promote events
- find alumni in your area

The Forum is monitored by a small editorial team of volunteers who will respond to any questions or direct them to the Data Schools instructors/researchers if necessary.

One of the moderators is **Annajiat Alim Rasel**. Read on to find out more about him and why he volunteered to monitor the Forum.

Introduce yourself!

I am Annajiat Alim Rasel, a Sr. Lecturer at the School of Data and Sciences at Brac University, Dhaka, Bangladesh. I work at the Department of Computer Science and Engineering. I mostly taught problem solving in introductory programming language courses. I try to explore the exciting fields of Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Parallel, Distributed and High-Performance Computing (HPC).

Where did you become acquainted with the RDA and CODATA? Which CODATA-RDA School did you attend and what was your experience?

I learnt about RDA and CODATA from [The Carpentries](#). I was a helper in the “2021 CODATA RDA Research Data Science Summer School”. It was a positive and a learning experience.

What has motivated you to get more involved? You were the helper in the “2021 CODATA RDA Research Data Science Summer School”, talk about your experience there.

opportunity for all the learners. Instructors and tutors helped both during the weekly zoom meetings as well as asynchronously using matrix element chat groups for each topic. It facilitated focused discussions and building on what was learnt. The combination of open source materials, Moodle recordings, discussion sessions, continuous follow up using group and individual chats with tutors and instructors provided an immersive experience for me as well as the learners.

How do you envisage the Forum? How is it different from stack overflow or other sites that have a similar purpose?

I envision the forum as a platform for high quality exchanges among the community members. I believe that it would be a safe learning environment, where learners are allowed to dream and ponder, both practical and hypothetical open ended questions are welcome, anyone can get feedback on their approach to solving the problems in their own domains, etc. Other websites are very restrictive and may not be able to ensure encouraging and learner friendly environments.

In your opinion, what are the must have skills and knowledge for someone who wants to be a data scientist?

I believe that the following skills and knowledge are essential for data scientists:

- Coding
- Data Wrangling
- Data Visualization
- Machine Learning
- High-Performance Computing

Data Steward Open Events Nov-Dec 2021

Katie Yates, STFC

[FAIRsFAIR](#) and [EOSC Synergy](#) recently ran two open call Data Steward training events. Each event ran over three half days, during the last week of November and first week of December. Unlike previous Data Steward training events, both workshops were open to attendees from any country or institution. With the first workshop being held during the morning while the second was run later in the afternoon to accommodate participants across different time zones. In total 68 individuals attended across the two events representing a total of 56 institutions from 25 different countries.

more experience can share their knowledge with those just getting started. Both workshops covered a range of topics including an introduction to RDM, FAIR, Data Management Planning and Responsible and Open Research, before moving on to Pedagogy and how to effectively design and create training courses.

This was my first time as an instructor delivering a session on Research Data Management service provision. During the session, attendees were introduced to the Research Infrastructure Self-Evaluation (RISE) framework, a benchmarking tool designed to facilitate RDM service planning and development, before moving into breakout groups for further discussion focusing on one of the following areas of the framework: Advisory services, DMPs and Training. The discussion provided attendees with the opportunity to hear from other organisations about the services they offered, as well as the challenges faced and successes achieved whilst developing and implementing their RDM services.

Perfect combination of theoretical knowledge understandable for novices but useful even for experts, with practical exercises where all the questions are answered. Agnieszka Cybulska, attendee

Data Schools Advisory Board

On 4th and 8th March 2022 an Advisory Board for the schools was set up. This board is made up of 12 members and will meet twice a year. The role of the Board is to:

- Assist and advise the Data Schools and the 'founding organisations' with planning and implementing a sustainability and expansion model.
- Advise and oversee strategic development of the schools and help ensure good and transparent governance.
- Advise on the development of a business plan and sustainability model.
- In due course, advise on any recruitment which may need to be taken (understanding that the specific appointment may be made by a partner institution)

The members are:

Chris Erdmann (AGU)

Paola González Vargas (UNA, Costa Rica)

Marjan Grootveld (DANS, Netherlands)

[Subscribe](#)[Past Issues](#)[Translate ▼](#)

Christine Kirkpatrick (UCSD)

Devika Madalli (Indian Statistical Institute)

Tshiamo Motshegwa (AOSP)

Annette Ouattara (Université Nangui Abrogoua, Côte d'Ivoire)

Wouter Schallier (United Nations, Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean)

Kathryn Unsworth (ARDC)

Elizabeth Bruce (Microsoft)

The advice of the Advisory Board members will be essential as the schools organisation grows in terms of the number of schools provided and in developing the necessary infrastructure to enable that.

Alumni Profile

Motahareh Hakimi

Hello there!

I am Motahareh Hakiminejad, a Computational Biologist based in Iran. I studied Biotechnology and I am currently doing my master's in Biophysics at the University of Tehran, Iran.

To give a little context about why I think data science is essential in biology, I must say that traditionally, biologists thought that to know a living being, you

big picture. We have tons and tons of data available and a lab - our computer - to test our hypothesis on these data. Instead of singling out parts of an animal and scrutinizing them individually, I think Biologists should find a way to see the big picture.

During my studies, I came across the problem of finding cancer-driving mutations among the plethora of non-cancerous mutations. My dissertation is to develop a machine learning tool to identify driver mutations based on the effect of mutation on protein rather than the mutation frequency. I try to combine the biophysical perspective of how mutations can affect proteins with cancer genomics and develop an R package to predict the effect of mutations. I work with cancer genomic data, make feature sets and build a model which gets a mutation and gives back a score indicating whether or not it can contribute to cancer development. Such tools can help practitioners diagnose cancer more effectively and prescribe drugs based on the protein affected since various genetic events can drive cancer.

As a Biologist by training, I had to learn data science skills for my thesis. In 2021, I participated in "The CODATA RDA Research Data Science Summer School" (6 September - 19 November 2021). This school was a great experience: I learned the coding skills necessary for my project and building a package, how data should be presented, and I became familiar with the concept of "responsible conduct of research," which I've found crucial for every researcher. But, most importantly, I learned how a group of committed and kind researchers could gather to make such a fantastic learning opportunity for people all over the globe.

I plan to pursue my studies in computational biology and data science and want to give back to other researchers by teaching data science skills, like coding. I enjoy birding and hiking in my spare time, and I really enjoy meeting new people, so feel free to contact me.

I am available by email (mot.hakimi.95@gmail.com). I'm also on Twitter (<https://twitter.com/MotHakimi>) and LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/in/motahareh-hakiminejad-7840471b7/>).

Alumni Profile

Nicolaie Constaninescu

The Summer School is a place to gain basic competences, and sharpen existing ones. For me, a digital humanities researcher, this was the best opportunity to gain a professional insight into how, and what a practitioner should look into when collecting, cleaning, working, and extracting valuable conclusions.

Humanities field is in rapid change geared by the new generation of NLP (Natural Language Processing), and Machine Learning tools. In respect to my field - Library and Information Science, participation in this School gave me plenty of ideas based on its courses' structure and content for a Summer School I'm involved with back at home. This was also one of the reasons I signed up for the 2021 School as well. I needed a hands-on approach model, and I did find a solid one for developing further the local curricula.

Data is the central point for all the learning materials starting from policies, going through practical data wrangling, analysis, and to exploration of datasets followed by case study immersion. I appreciated the medium effort required for getting through the courses, but the concepts and the practical programming stages are expanding in need for time allocation, growing beyond every day exercise in the case of a trained scientist.

You have to be prepared to learn fast, and document what you do beyond the confinements of the exercises. For me, being used to programming was a fun and rewarding challenge which led me to appreciate more statistics, and data wrangling in general.

The management policies and ethical concerns with regards to data were also welcomed, setting the stage for a better perception of the context in which research and datasets are merged forming the complex stages of Open Science.

and this proved to be a good model setting a pace which left the students with time for reflection.

I would like to thank every teacher and instructor for their precious time dedicated to the 2021 year.

Per aspera ad astra.

Nicolaie Constantinescu, Transilvania University of Braşov

Data Schools Moodle Course

Katie Yates, STFC

[FAIRsFAIR](#) together with [EOSC Synergy](#) recently launched an [online Data Steward Training course](#) developed using the materials from the Data Steward Instructor Training Workshops run throughout 2020 and 2021. The objective of the course is to equip participants from universities or research-performing organisations with data stewardship skills and knowledge to better support researchers.

This is an introductory level course aimed at anyone looking to start a career in Data Stewardship. Through a combination of recorded presentations, assignments and quizzes, participants will gain the skills and knowledge required to be successful data steward.

The course is broken down into five self-paced modules each taking on average one hour to complete. Topics covered include: FAIR and open data, learning pedagogy and training design, open and responsible research, data management planning, and RDM service delivery. All five modules are introductory, allowing learners to choose to follow them all or pick the ones that are most relevant to them. By the end of this course learners will:

- Be able to explain the difference between FAIR and Open Data to researchers.
- Be able to develop training courses using open learning resources.
- Understand the range of skills and knowledge associated with data stewardship.
- Be able to identify areas where collaboration on service provision is most beneficial.

The course is proudly hosted on the [EOSC Synergy learn Moodle platform](#), which offers a range of courses and services for researchers and research support staff.

[Subscribe](#)[Past Issues](#)[Translate](#) ▼

SMART-DART: Health Equity: Supporting Minority and Regional Training in Data & AI for Researchers of Tomorrow: Health Equity Cohort. Sept-Nov 2022

The CODATA-RDA Schools of Research Data Science collaborates with The South Big Data Innovation Hub in the United States

The South Big Data Innovation Hub - a community convener for data innovation has a vision to mobilize the data science community to collectively accelerate scientific discovery and innovation, spur economic development in the region, broaden participation and diversity in data science, and address societal challenges affecting the Southern United States.

Further details [here](#).

Have you enjoyed reading the newsletter? Do you have ideas for future editions? Get involved in the Alumni WG and be part of a volunteer editorial team! Just email us at dataschools@codata.org

Our mailing address is:

dataschools@codata.org

[Unsubscribe from this list](#)

This email was sent to <<Email Address>>

[why did I get this?](#) [unsubscribe from this list](#) [update subscription preferences](#)

CODATA-RDA Schools for Research Data Science · Rutherford Appleton Laboratory · Harwell, Didcot · Oxford, Oxfordshire OX11 0QX · United Kingdom

[Subscribe](#)

[Past Issues](#)

[Translate](#) ▼

